

Hephaisteion

also known as “Temple of Hephaistos”

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The Hephaisteion was an temple to the Greek god Hephaestus located on the Kolonos Agoraios hill overlooking the Athenian Agora to the east. This placement was especially meaningful because it kept this god of craftsmen close to both the Industrial District and the commercial center. According to the Roman traveler Pausanias, Athena, goddess of craft, was worshiped alongside him and present in the cult statue. This Doric temple was built mostly of marble, and its sculptural decoration featuring a centauromachy (frieze) and the labors of the Athenian hero Theseus (metopes) emphasized the eastern end that was most visible to those in the Agora below. The Hephaisteion notably provides evidence of the landscaping of sanctuaries; planting pits and vessels dating to the third century BCE were excavated throughout the precinct. Although not treated in this entry, this temple had a long and varied religious life through its conversion to a Christian church (7th c. CE) and use as a Protestant cemetery (19th c. CE).

Date Range: 480 BCE - 267 CE

Region: Hephaisteion

Region tags: Greece, Attica

Temple of Hephaistos, hill west of Athenian Agora

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

General Variables

Sources and Excavations

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Camp, J. *The Athenian Agora: Excavations in the Heart of Classical Athens* (1986)
- Source 2: Dinsmoor, W. *Observations on the Hephaisteion*. *Hesperia Supplements* 5. (Princeton 1941)
- Source 3: Miles, M.M. “Constructing Architects: The So-Called ‘Theseum Architect,’” in *Artists and Artistic Production in Ancient Greece*, ed. K. Seaman and P. Schultz, 101-123 (Cambridge: 2017)

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://pleiades.stoa.org/places/558659669>

- Source 1 Description: entry in Pleiades, a community-built gazetteer and graph of ancient places
- Source 2 URL: <http://agora.ascsa.net/id/agora/monument/temple%20of%20hephaistos?q=&t=monument&v=list&sort=&s=71>
- Source 2 Description: Online database of the Athenian Agora Excavations (entry: monument, Hephaisteion)
- Source 3 URL: <https://topostext.org/place/380237SHep>
- Source 3 Description: entry in ToposText, an indexed collection of ancient texts and mapped places relevant the the history and mythology of the ancient Greeks

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

– Yes

Type of excavation:

– Scientific

Years of excavation:

– Year range: 1930s

Notes: a few small archaeological interventions (such as excavating around the statue base) were done by German and Greek archaeologists in the late 1800s

Name of excavation

– Official or descriptive name: Excavations of the Athenian Agora (American School of Classical Studies at Athens)

Topographical Context

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

– Elevation

Type of elevation

– Hill

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– Yes

Type of feature

- Water feature
- Plantings

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– Yes

↳ Is there a distinct boundary between the place and the urban fabric:
– Yes

↳ Is the place located significantly within the urban fabric:
Is the place centrally located, or at the crossroads of significant pathways?
– Yes

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– No

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– No

Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

Notes: Temple of Hephaistos

↳ A single structure
– Yes

↳ The structure has a definite shape
– Rectangular

↳ A group of structures:
– No

↳ A group of features:
– No

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

– Yes

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

– Worship

↳ Worship:

– Communal

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:

– No

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:

– No

– Yes

Notes: planting pits

↳ A single structure

– No

↳ One single feature

– Purposefully placed plants

↳ A group of structures:

– No

↳ A group of features:

– No

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

– Yes

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

– Other [specify]: aesthetics

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:

– Yes

Notes: individual plants couldn't last that long, but the pots used suggest replanting over time

↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:

– Yes

↳ How was the structure/feature destroyed

– Other [specify]: unknown

↳ Was it destroyed deliberately:

– Other [specify]: unknown

↳ Was it destroyed by accident/natural phenomena:

– Other [specify]: unknown

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:

– No

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– Yes

Dedicated to a supernatural being:

– Yes [specify]: Hephaistos

Dedicated to more than one supernatural being:

– Yes [specify]: Athena

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– No

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– Yes

Specify

– Other [specify]: government of the city of Athens

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– Field doesn't know

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– No

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– Field doesn't know

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– Field doesn't know

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– No

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

– Other [specify]: field does not know

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– No

Design and Material Remains

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– No

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– Yes

↳ In the average place, what percentage of area is taken up by built monuments:

– Percentage: 50

↳ Footprint of largest single religious monument, square meters:

Please add dimensions in the comments, if known.

– Square meters: 525

Notes: 13.71 m x 38.24 m

↳ Height of largest single religious monument, meters:

– Height, meters: 5.71

↳ Size of average monument, square meters:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Height of average monument, meters:

– Field doesn't know

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Yes

↳ Earth

– No

↳ Sand

– No

↳ Clay

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Plaster

– No

↳ Wood

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Grass

– No

↳ Stone

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– No

Notes: sculptures use island marble

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

– No

Decoration

Is decoration present:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration part of the building (permanent):

– Yes

↳ On the outside:

– Yes

↳ On the inside:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration attached to the building, i.e. movable reliefs or tapestries

– Yes

↳ Is the decoration figural:

A figural representation is defined here as one that contains the depiction of discernible human, anthropomorphic, animal, or zoomorphic forms. In general, it differentiates between animate and inanimate beings, as well as between narrative compositions and still life, landscapes, abstraction, etc. Answer [Yes] for each type of figure depicted

– Yes

↳ Are there gods depicted:

– Yes

↳ Are there other supernatural beings depicted:

– Yes

↳ Are there humans depicted:

– Yes

↳ Are there animals depicted:

– Yes

↳ Are there animal-human hybrids depicted:

– Yes

↳ Is the decoration non-figural:

– Yes

↳ Is it geometric/abstract

– No

↳ Floral motifs

– Yes

↳ Is it writing/caligraphy

– No

↳ Is the decoration hidden or restricted from view:

– No

↳ Are there statues present:

– Yes

↳ Cult statues:

– Yes

↳ Statues of gods/supernatural beings:

– No

↳ Statues of humans:

– No

↳ Are there reliefs present:

A relief as opposed to sculpture carved on the round is a work of sculpture in which the figures project from a background support, generally a flat surface. Reliefs can be carved out of stone, clay, or a similar material.

– Yes

↳ Reliefs representing the god(s) worshipped at the place:

– No

↳ Reliefs representing mythological narratives:

– Yes

↳ Reliefs representing human/historical narratives:

– No

↳ Are there paintings present:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there mosaics present:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there inscriptions as part of the decoration:

– No

Iconography

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– Yes

↳ Eyes (stylized or not)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic)

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract)

– No

↳ Portrayals of afterlife

– No

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols)

– No

↳ Humans

– No

↳ Supernatural narratives

– Yes

↳ Human narratives

– No

Beliefs and Practices

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– No

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– No

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– No

Supernatural Beings

Is a supreme high god is present:

– No

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are previously human spirits present:

– No

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– Yes

↳ Nonhuman spirits can be seen:

– I don't know

Notes: this question is under the nonhuman heading

↳ Nonhuman spirits can be physically felt:

– I don't know

Notes: this question is under the nonhuman heading

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– No

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– Yes

↳ Is the cult statue visible:

– Yes

↳ Is the cult statue hidden:

– No

Supernatural Interactions

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– Field doesn't know

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Do visitors communicate with gods:

– Yes

↳ Do visitors communicate with other supernatural beings:

– No

Ritual and Performance

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– Yes

↳ Are there animal sacrifices:

– Yes [specify]: which animals is unknown (presumably cow, sheep, goat, pig)

↳ Are there human sacrifices:

– No

↳ Are the sacrificed humans associated in some way:

– I don't know

Notes: N/A: there are no sacrificed humans

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– No

Are material offerings present:

– Yes

↳ Are material offerings mandatory:

– No

↳ Are material offerings composed of valuable objects:

– Yes

↳ Are material offerings composed of daily-life objects:

– Yes

- ↳ Are material offerings interred at this place (in caches):
 - No

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:
– No

Is maintenance of the place performed:
– Yes

- ↳ Is it required:
 - Yes

- ↳ Is there cleansing (for the maintenance):
 - Yes

- ↳ Are there periodic repairs/reconstructions:
 - Yes

- ↳ Is the maintenance performed by permanent staff:
 - Field doesn't know

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:
– Field doesn't know

Is this place a venue for feasting:
– Field doesn't know

Are festivals present:
– Field doesn't know

Notes: There were several festivals in Athens that involved Hephaistos, but whether they used this spot is unknown and/or disputed.

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:

– No

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– No

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– Yes

↳ Do large-scale rituals take place:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Do small-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

↳ On average how many participants are present in large-scale rituals:

– specify: unknown whether they take place here

↳ How often do these rituals take place:

– specify: unknown

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

– No

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

– Yes

↳ Are there synchronic practices:

– No

↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual:

– No

Institutions and Scriptures

Religious Specialists

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– No

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– No

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– No

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– Yes

Bureaucracy

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– Field doesn't know

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– Yes

Is this control the primary supporting income of this place:

– No

Does this place lease out land:

– No

Does this place lease out tools:

– No

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– No

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– No

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– No

Bibliography

General References

Reference: Hephaisteion, Camp II, John McK.. The Athenian Agora. ASCSA, 2003.
https://books.google.com/books/about/The_Athenian_Agora.html?hl=&id=qwkjM_fxqA8C.

Reference: Hephaisteion, Camp II, John McK.. The Athenian Agora. American School of Classical Studies at Athens, 2010. https://books.google.com/books/about/The_Athenian_Agora.html?hl=&id=EriZDwAAQBAJ.

Reference: Hephaisteion, Dinsmoor, William Bell. Observations on the Hephaisteion. American School of Classical Studies at Athens, n.d..
https://www.ascsa.edu.gr/uploads/media/oa_ebooks/oa_hesperia_supplements/HS5.pdf.